

MAESTRO: Multi-Agent Expert System for Task-Routed Operations

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Abstract

We present MAESTRO (Multi-Agent Expert System for Task-Routed Operations), our solution to the SoccerNet VQA Challenge 2026, achieving **96.0%** on the held-out challenge set. Our approach is a knowledge-grounded system built on Claude Sonnet 4.6: (1) metadata-driven context construction that maps material paths to Game Dataset event annotations and SoccerWiki entity profiles, and (2) cost-efficient inference via the Anthropic Batch API with task-specific prompts across 14 specialist sub-agents.

1. Method

The SoccerNet VQA Challenge [1] presents 500 multiple-choice questions spanning 14 task categories across text, image, and video modalities. MAESTRO is a **master-router + specialist-agent** pipeline built on Claude Sonnet 4.6 [2]. A routing agent infers the task category from the $q\{N\}$ sub-folder in each question’s material path (absent for text-only tasks) and dispatches to one of 14 specialist sub-agents, each with a dedicated system prompt and context pipeline. Two knowledge sources are shared across agents: SoccerWiki [3] and the Game Dataset.

1.1. Background Knowledge QA

These questions carry no materials; the entity name appears in the question text. The agent extracts the name, fetches the exact SoccerWiki record, and reads the answer directly (career clubs, nationality, position, stats). Ground truth is anchored to SoccerWiki, so a correct fetch is deterministic.

1.2. Match Situation QA

These questions carry no materials; match identity (date, teams) is stated in the question text. The agent fetches the exact Game Dataset record (exact date-string match, embedding fallback) and reads the answer: score, formations, corner counts, yellow card timestamps, substitutions.

1.3. Camera Status Classification

Single broadcast image; classify into one of 13 camera types.

1.4. Background Knowledge Image QA

Three-step: (1) Claude Vision identifies the player by name from the photo; (2) the name retrieves the SoccerWiki entity; (3) the specialist answers with the full profile as context. Where SoccerWiki has no entry, a supplementary web search fills the gap.

1.5. Jersey Number Recognition

Material is a folder of ~ 575 player-tracking images (same player, multiple moments). The agent stride-samples up to 25 frames (stride = total/25) for diverse viewpoints and reads the clearest digit. Answer options are a tight cluster of adjacent numbers (e.g., 24, 25, 26), providing a validation check.

1.6. Score/Time QA

All items include a broadcast image; Claude Vision reads the scoreboard directly. When the question names a specific match (e.g., “Liverpool vs Aston Villa, 2019-20”), the agent additionally fetches the Game Dataset record and injects relevant statistics (corners, goals) for questions beyond what is visible.

1.7. Game State QA

Given a wide broadcast image, the question asks how many players from one team are in an attacking or defending position. The agent counts only players with at least half their body visible, eliminating the systematic over-counting bias observed with permissive prompts.

1.8. Camera Status Switching

Given a short video clip, the task is to classify the type of camera transition that occurs. The agent samples 8 uniform frames and identifies the transition type from the visual sequence.

1.9. Replay Grounding

One replay clip vs. four candidate action clips; identify which candidate clip matches the replay. Train/valid materials carry full match paths, but test/challenge sets use anonymized numeric IDs (e.g., `q9/replay/28.mp4`), so

metadata matching is not possible. The agent compares visual content directly; each clip is sampled at 4 uniform frames.

1.10. Action Classification

The material path encodes match and exact timestamp (e.g., 2_25_28.mp4 = half 2, 25:28). The agent retrieves the nearest Game Dataset event (± 10 s) and receives its `comments_type` label, one of 24 categories that map directly to the four options, reducing inference to text matching. Video frames around the event confirm the action when the retrieved label is ambiguous.

1.11. Commentary Generation QA

The path encodes exact match and timestamp. The agent looks up the Game Dataset event at that second; the `comments_text_anonymized` field is the factual source of the answer choices. Retrieval is deterministic.

1.12. Commentary Relevant QA

The path timestamp indexes the Game Dataset event; the non-anonymized `comments_text` identifies the player performing the described action. That name retrieves the SoccerWiki record for the career question. Video frames around the event confirm the action when commentary is ambiguous.

1.13. Jersey Color QA

The material path identifies both the match and the exact timestamp (e.g., 1_34_52.mp4 = half 1, 34:52). The agent loads the Game Dataset match JSON, which contains `home_jersey_color` and `away_jersey_color` in `match_info`, and retrieves the event at that timestamp. The event commentary names the team performing the action (e.g., “Gabriel Jesus (Manchester City) penalised for an offensive foul”), allowing the agent to resolve home vs. away and read the correct kit color directly. Sampled frames from the clip are also provided for visual confirmation, but the metadata answer takes priority. GT annotation disagreements for this category are analyzed in Section 2.1.

1.14. Multi-view Foul Recognition

Up to 4 camera views, 5 frames each (20-image limit). Materials use opaque action IDs (e.g., `action_113`) in all splits, with no match or timestamp metadata available. The agent classifies contact incidents directly from visual evidence; chain-of-thought prompting was omitted as it induced over-analysis of ambiguous contact.

2. Results

Challenge set. Our system achieves **96.0%** on the held-out challenge set. Per-category breakdowns are not released by

the evaluation server; task-level analysis uses the test set with available ground truth.

Test-set performance. Table 1 reports test-set accuracy across all 14 categories (94.8%). Our system performs exceptionally well across all categories that leverage structured text retrieval, including background knowledge, match situation, commentary, and action classification tasks. Lower scores have structural explanations: game state QA suffers off-by-one counting in wide broadcast shots; foul recognition reflects the inherent difficulty of classifying ambiguous contact across multiple views; jersey color QA contains items where the GT annotation disagrees with game metadata (Section 2.1).

Table 1. Per-category accuracy on the test set. † See Section 2.1.

Task	Corr.	Tot.	Acc.
Background Knowledge QA	62	62	100.0%
Match Situation QA	73	73	100.0%
Action Classification	47	50	94.0%
Commentary Generation QA	50	50	100.0%
Commentary Relevant QA	40	40	100.0%
Jersey Number Recognition	10	10	100.0%
Score/Time QA	28	30	93.3%
Camera Status Classification	17	20	85.0%
Camera Status Switching	17	20	85.0%
Replay Grounding	19	20	95.0%
Background Knowledge Image	46	50	92.0%
Game State QA	22	25	88.0%
Multi-view Foul Recognition	12	15	80.0%
Jersey Color QA [†]	31	35	88.6%
Total	474	500	94.8%

Ablation. Table 2 shows cumulative gains from each pipeline component.

Table 2. Cumulative ablation on test set.

Configuration	Score	Acc.
Claude Sonnet 4.6 (base)	393/500	78.6%
+ Game Dataset event injection	430/500	86.0%
+ SoccerWiki RAG	452/500	90.4%
+ Master router CoT + subagent re-confirmation	474/500	94.8%

2.1. Jersey Color QA: GT Annotation Analysis

Jersey color QA scores 88.6% despite our pipeline prioritizing kit colors read directly from the Game Dataset match JSON (`home_jersey_color` / `away_jersey_color`). On the 4 remaining incorrect items, the game metadata provides a clear answer that our system selects, yet it disagrees with the benchmark ground truth, indicating the error lies in the GT annotation rather than in the retrieval. We recommend future benchmark versions audit per-match kit color labels for consistency with the Game Dataset records.

References

- [1] Jiayuan Rao, Zifeng Li, Haoning Wu, Ya Zhang, Yanfeng Wang, and Weidi Xie. Multi-agent system for comprehensive soccer understanding. In *ACM Int. Conf. Multimedia*, 2025. 1
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